

STRESS DISTRIBUTION IN AN ANTICLINE; A NUMERICAL APPROACH.

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It is general experience of geoscientists that all the rocks are affected at all the scales by fault and fracture systems due to the application of stress fields different in origins and timing.

A fractured reservoir is a kind of anisotropic reservoir where the faults/fractures play the main role or as storage or as barrier on the flow of the contained fluids or gas.

In the evaluation and development of a fractured reservoir is critical task to define the fracture system/s location. In this project the numerical modelling (Finite Element Method) was successfully applied to investigate the relationships between the state of stress and the fracture systems distribution in the case of the Mohr Coulomb fracture law.

The experimental procedure was: a) construct a balanced geological cross section of the host structure (geological model); b) mechanically characterise each lithologic unit; c) discretize (meshing) the model.

To the discretized model was applied a stress field (regional stress field) and, in the range of elastic deformation, the principal stress components module and orientation in each point of the mesh were calculated.

A better knowledge of these processes will improve oil field performances, dynamic reservoir modelling, recovery and stimulation planning.

Fig. 1: Geomechanic model of an NE-SW running cross section through the M.Catria anticline. The model is based on surface geology field data.

RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN GROUNDWATER SYSTEMS AND TECTONIC STRUCTURES IN THE WESTERN VENETO FOOTHILLS

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The Venetian foothills between Lake Garda to the west and San Bonifacio to the east, can be subdivided into four different areas by means of chemical and physical characters of geothermal groundwaters:

-a northern one with cold Ca or Ca-Mg rich waters ($T < 18.8$ °C) belonging to a very rapid karst circulation characterized by reduced water-rock interactions. The presumed reservoir are the Jurassic Limestones and /or the Dolomia Principale Formation;

-a southern sector located in the Caldiero area, characterized by water T up to 28 °C and sulphate-rich due to the reactions with evaporitic rocks. These waters show a circuit deeper and slower than the previous one, characterized by more pervasive water-rock interactions;

-a western area located between Lazise and Pescantina villages characterized by T up to 35 °C and Cl-Na rich composition due to crystalline basement-water interactions. At Lazise the geothermal waters show a deep circuit, as confirmed by the attainment of rock-water equilibrium. This water show strong temperature and chemistry variations depending on mixing with surface waters;

-a transition area located at the boundary between Lazise and Caldiero zones characterized by cold Na-K rich water due to interactions with clay sediments.

The lineaments recognized by satellite image interpretation (Landsat 5 TM) can be grouped on the basis of their attitude into four major systems, some of them related to the geothermal source distributions:

-the NNE-SSW lineaments belongs to the Giudicarie fault system, and they are constituted by the Baldo, M. Pastello and Bosco Chiesanuova faults, and other minor structures;